

The effect of the Collatz operation on odd integers of the form $4k - 1$

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1 Introduction

In this paper, we investigate the effect of the Collatz map on odd integers of the form $4k - 1$ by solving this recurrence relation

$$\begin{cases} x_0 = t \\ x_{i+1} = \begin{cases} \frac{3x_i + 1}{2} & x_i \bmod 2 = 1 \\ \frac{x_i}{2} & x_i \bmod 2 = 0 \end{cases} \end{cases}$$

and treating the recurrence relation as a Collatz operation.

Keywords: Collatz operation, odd integers of the form $4k - 1$

Attention.

1. In this paper, to avoid reading difficulties, the word “” is sometimes used in the text to indicate mathematical formulae.
2. The variables in this paper are assumed to be natural numbers unless otherwise specified.

2 Root sequence

For an initial value of n , the sequence $\{N_i\}$ is given by

$$\begin{cases} N_0 = n \\ N_{i+1} = \frac{N_i}{\text{rad}(N_i)} \end{cases}$$

where “rad” is the *root function*, i.e., the product of distinct prime factors of a number.¹

¹For example, $\text{rad}(18) = 2 \cdot 3 = 6$. In addition, for convenience, we define $\text{rad}(1) = 1$.

This is called the “root sequence” of n , and $\{N_i\}$ is written $n\{i\}$ below. The marginal-2 elimination number of n is defined as follows and written as $\mathbb{X}(n)$.

$$\mathbb{X}(n) = \min\{k \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\} \mid \cos(n\{k\} \cdot \pi) = -1\}$$

(For any non-empty set A , let $\min A$ be a function that returns the smallest element of A).

$$f(x) \triangleq \begin{cases} \frac{x}{2} & \text{if } x \equiv 0 \pmod{2} \\ 3x + 1 & \text{if } x \equiv 1 \pmod{2} \end{cases}$$

f is called the Collatz map.

3 Certain asymptotic formulas

Consider the following recurrence relation^[1]:

$$\begin{cases} x_0 = 4x - 1 \\ x_{n+1} = \frac{3x_n + 1}{2} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Lemma 1.

$$x_n = 4\left(\frac{3}{2}\right)^n x - 1$$

Proof. The characteristic equation of the recurrence relation (1) is as follows:

$$\alpha = \frac{3\alpha + 1}{2}$$

Solve this to get “ $\alpha = -1$ ”.

Summing up equation (1) by subtracting α from the expression for x_{n+1} in equation (1), we get:

$$x_{n+1} + 1 = \frac{3}{2}(x_n + 1)$$

Therefore, the sequence x_n can be regarded as a sequence of equal ratios with an initial term x_0 and a common ratio $\frac{3}{2}$. Put “ $y_n = x_n + 1$ ”,

$$\begin{aligned} y_{n+1} &= \frac{3}{2}y_n \\ &= \left(\frac{3}{2}\right)^2 y_{n-1} \\ &= \left(\frac{3}{2}\right)^3 y_{n-2} \\ &= \dots \\ &= \left(\frac{3}{2}\right)^{n+1} y_0 \end{aligned}$$

Put y_n back to $x_n + 1$ to get

$$x_{n+1} + 1 = \left(\frac{3}{2}\right)^{n+1}(x_0 + 1)$$

from “ $x_0 = 4x - 1$ ”,

$$\begin{aligned} x_{n+1} + 1 &= \left(\frac{3}{2}\right)^{n+1}\{(4x - 1) + 1\} \\ &= 4\left(\frac{3}{2}\right)^{n+1}x \\ x_{n+1} &= 4\left(\frac{3}{2}\right)^{n+1}x - 1 \end{aligned}$$

Replace “ $n + 1$ ” with n (Note that now $n = 0$ can also be calculated, but by buying the range $n > 0$),

$$x_n = 4\left(\frac{3}{2}\right)^n x - 1$$

□

Now, can we not think of the x_{n+1} part of equation (1) of this gradual equation (it would be more appropriate to call it a sequence of numbers, but since it is difficult to understand, we will unify it) as the application of the Collatz operation twice on the odd number x_n ? To this end, let us prove that x_n is odd (given certain conditions in n).

Lemma 2.

For $i < \mathbb{X}(x) + 2$, x_i is an odd number.

Proof. For $i < \mathbb{X}(x) + 3$, $4\left(\frac{3}{2}\right)^i x \in \mathbb{N}$ is valid. However, since $4\left(\frac{3}{2}\right)^i x$ becomes odd when $i = \mathbb{X}(x) + 2$, $4\left(\frac{3}{2}\right)^i x - 1$ becomes even, which is not valid as a proof, so, although somewhat aggressive, let $i = \mathbb{X}(x) + 1$ be the upper bound. Then x_i for any natural number i less than or equal to i is odd.

□

4 Identities of gradual formulae and Collatz maps and derived theorem groups

From Lemma2, this graded formula can be regarded as a two-time application of the Collatz operation (note that the integer property is broken at $i > \mathbb{X}(x) + 1$, but x_i is a natural number).

From the above, this gradualisation formula can be rewritten as follows for $n + 1 < \mathbb{X}(x) + 3$ (where the letter to the right of f indicates the number of iterations):

$$\begin{cases} x_0 = 4x - 1 \\ x_{n+1} = f^2(x_n) \end{cases}$$

. Continue to deploy x_n further.

$$x_{n+1} = f^{2(n+1)}(4x - 1)$$

From these we obtain the following relationship. Replace $n + 1$ by n to obtain

$$x_n = f^{2n}(4x - 1)$$

(note that the range goes from $1 < n + 1 < \mathbb{X}(x) + 3$ to $0 < n < \mathbb{X}(x) + 2$)
From these we obtain the following relationship.

Theorem 1.

For any $0 < n < \mathbb{X}(x) + 2$,

$$f^{2n}(4x - 1) = 4\left(\frac{3}{2}\right)^n x - 1$$

From these lemmas, we derive the following theorems.

Theorem 2.

$$2\left(\frac{3}{2}\right)^{\mathbb{X}(x)+1} x + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$$

Proof. The negation of this proposition follows:

$$3\left(\frac{3}{2}\right)^{\mathbb{X}(x)} x + 1 \equiv 1 \pmod{2} \quad (2)$$

$$\therefore 3\left(\frac{3}{2}\right)^{\mathbb{X}(x)} x \equiv 0 \pmod{2} \quad (3)$$

The left-hand side of this equation can be transformed as follows:

$$3^{\mathbb{X}(x)+1} \cdot \left(\frac{x}{2^{\mathbb{X}(x)}}\right)$$

Where " $\frac{x}{2^{\mathbb{X}(x)}}$ " is a prime factor not containing 2, also " $3^{\mathbb{X}(x)+1}$ " does not contain 2 in the prime factors. Equation (3) is therefore incorrect. Hence, equation (2) is also wrong. From these, the proof by the backward reasoning is complete. □

By the way, this conclusion is " $\frac{3\left(\frac{3}{2}\right)^{\mathbb{X}(x)} x + 1}{2} \in \mathbb{N}$ ". When the part " $\frac{3\left(\frac{3}{2}\right)^{\mathbb{X}(x)} x + 1}{2}$," of in this equation is $\mathcal{A}(x)$, " $4\mathcal{A}(x) - 3$ " is a natural number from **Theorem 1**. In other words, the theorem implies that " $f^{2(\mathbb{X}(x)+1)}(4x - 1)$ is odd integers of the form $4k - 3$ " (Granted, I gave a value in anticipation of this kind of conclusion).

The main content of this paper has now been shown, but finally (sorry to crush a little hope), we show (with apologies to those who may be disappointed) that it is only for $\mathcal{A}(x)$ in **Theorem 2** that a $4k-1$ odd integers of the form $4k-1$ becomes a odd integers of the form $4k-3$ by the relational formula of **Theorem 1**, that is, when a odd integers of the form $4k-1$ becomes a odd integers of the form $4k-3$, the Collatz I will show that the minimum number of operations is $2(\mathbb{X}(x) + 1)$.

Theorem 3.

$$\min\{i \in \mathbb{N} | \exists! k \in \mathbb{N}, f^{2(i+1)}(4x-1) = 4k-3\} = \mathbb{X}(x)$$

Proof. By transforming (or manipulating) equation

$$f^{2(i+1)}(4x-1) = 4\left(\frac{3}{2}\right)^{i+1} - 1 = 4k-3$$

, we obtain

$$k = \frac{2\left(\frac{3}{2}\right)^{i+1} + 1}{2}$$

For k to be even, the prime factor of 2 in the first term of the numerator is cancelled out by $\left(\frac{3}{2}\right)^{i+1}$, The first term of the numerator must be odd. Therefore, the first term of the numerator must be an odd number, since

$$\begin{aligned} i+1 &\geq \mathbb{X}(x) + 1 \\ \therefore i &\geq \mathbb{X}(x) \end{aligned}$$

(From the definition, $\mathbb{X}(x)$ denotes the number of prime factors of x , 2. In order to also eliminate 2 in the first term of the numerator, we need to add 1 to $\mathbb{X}(x)$. From this and **Theorem 2**, we obtain **Theorem 3**. \square)

(The reason these are calculated with “ $i+1$ ” instead of i is that the “ $4\left(\frac{3}{2}\right)^{n+1} - 1$ ” part of my notes was “ $6\left(\frac{3}{2}\right)^n - 1$ ” instead of “ $4\left(\frac{3}{2}\right)^{n+1} - 1$ ”)

$$C(x) \triangleq \frac{x}{2} \{(x+1) \bmod 2\} + \frac{3x+1}{2^{\max\{k \in \mathbb{N} | \frac{3x+1}{2^k}\}}}(x \bmod 2)$$

(For a set A , $\max A$ denotes “ $-\min A'$ ”, where A' is the set with only elements with the sign of the total elements of A reversed.)

There seem to be some papers that assume f to be $C^{[2]}$, but even for that **Theorem 1** holds with a slight change of conditions. This is because the operation of dividing by 2 of C when x_i is regarded as a function C is because the next number is odd after all from **Lemma 2**. **Theorem 2** does not directly depend on the number of Collatz operations, so it follows from **Theorem 1**. **Theorem 3** can also be covered by simply changing the number of iterations of f on the left-hand side.

$$\frac{4\left(\frac{3}{2}\right)^{\mathbb{X}(x)+1} - 1}{4x-1} \approx \left(\frac{3}{2}\right)^{\mathbb{X}(x)+1}$$

Thus, odd integers of the form $4k - 1$ increase roughly by a factor of $(\frac{3}{2})^{\mathbb{X}(x)+1}$. Thus, $4x - 1$ is increasing by a factor of $(\frac{3}{2})^{\mathbb{X}(x)+1}$ when the Collatz operation yields an odd integer of the form $4k - 3$.

5 References

- [1]Eduard Dyachenko,(2020).A proof of the Collatz conjecture and connection of intervals based on “tetrada”,pp.4,
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- [2]Erhan Tezcan,(2019).On Collatz Conjecture,pp.2
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